

SHORT TIMESCALE FLARES AS SIGNATURES OF X-RAY BINARIES

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ABSTRACT

We examine the X-ray flaring activity of accreting black holes vs. neutron stars in X-ray binaries using data from the Burst Alert Telescope (BAT) on SWIFT. Using data covering the period of 2007 March to 2013 June, we find flares on timescales of ~ 10 s and ~ 100 s. We search for properties of these flares that are shared by sources of the same type using two methods. We first find the power law for a differential frequency distribution of the flares, predicted by avalanche models of X-ray flaring. We then use two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests of similar sources, whereby we can compare the distributions in a nonparametric way. We find that the power laws may be indicators of an X-ray source's type. However, the K-S test did not reveal any evidence of similarity between flares from sources of the same kind. The similarity of these tests across numerous timescales, however, may be evidence of the fractal nature of accretion in these objects.

1. INTRODUCTION

Rapid X-ray variability has long been known to exist in accretion powered X-ray sources, such as black holes and neutron stars (e.g. Lamb 1975; Canizares & Oda 1977). Since these X-rays are thought to be emitted by a mechanism associated with the variable rate of matter falling into the accretion disk, such variability can be used to study the physical processes occurring in this regime. Furthermore, these mechanisms are expected to depend at least in part on the type of object they're associated with; e.g. the strong B-field from a pulsar must certainly affect the process of accretion, which may in turn alter the source's flaring activity. Various properties of X-ray flares have already been used to constrain either the mechanism or the dominant radiation process of their sources, such as fluence, peak flare intensity and flare time interval (e.g. Crosby et al. 1993; Negoro et al. 1995; Aschwanden & Freeland 2012; Neilsen 2013), and study objects ranging from black holes to our sun. Using recent BATSS data, it is now possible to observe such hard X-ray variability in many different sources on timescales as short as ~ 10 s (Krimm 2012). It therefore may be possible to determine what kind of object an X-ray source is by using certain flaring statistics on these short timescales.

Three different kinds of X-ray sources are investigated: black holes, pulsars, and low mass X-ray binaries containing low B-field neutron stars. Within each group, four sources were selected. The black holes include Cygnus X-1, GRS 1915+105, GX 339-4 and MAXI J1659-152, the pulsars include Centaurus X-3, Hercules X-1, MAXI J1409-619 and Vela X-1, and the other neutron stars include 4U 1700-377, GX 17+2, GX 349+2 and Scorpius X-1. The Crab is also used at several points to confirm that various pieces of code are working.

Power laws are fitted to the differential frequency distributions of the objects. Flaring, quantified in various ways, is thought to be one of the many natural phenomena that follow power laws. Such power laws have been both predicted theoretically (e.g. Mineshige 1994; Crosby 2011; Aschwanden 2013) and verified empirically (e.g. Crosby et al. 1993; Negoro et al. 1995). It is believed that the distribution of X-ray flares is the result of self-organized criticality (SOC), implying that the slope of the power law is related to the underlying physical mechanism of the nonlinear energy dissipation process which results in flaring.

We then compare sources using the two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. This test, operating on the empirical cumulative distribution functions of the two sources, allows for a nonparametric comparison of the sources. We can then determine the degree to which the flare distributions are similar.

2. OBSERVATIONS

2.1. Instruments

This study uses data from both the BAT's pointed operations and its slew survey. The BAT is one of three instruments on the *Swift* satellite Gehrels (2004), and serves as a hard X-ray transient monitor. The telescope relies on coded aperture imaging, which is a non-focusing technique often found in hard X-ray and γ -ray astronomy. Generally, this technique results in higher image background than with a true focusing telescope, but also allows for very large telescope fields of view and ~ 1 arcminute source localization. BAT possesses a wide field of view of $80^\circ \times 53^\circ$ (FWHM), observing nearly 1/9 of the sky at any given time. Each day, it covers around 80% of the sky in the 15-150keV band with detection sensitivity of 5.3mCrab, and is able to achieve time resolutions as fine as 64s (Krimm 2012).

While the BAT is optimized to detect transient GRBs, it also conducts a hard X-ray survey which can be used as an archival record of source flux variations (Barthelmy et al. 2005; Baumgartner et al. 2013). The survey provides these variations on timescales of single *Swift* pointings ranging from 64s to ~ 1000 s, as well as one-day averages. Light curves for 972 sources are provided on the publicly available monitor web page, along with the raw data in FITS format which is used in our analysis.

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FIG. 1.— Histograms of exposure lengths with means for two sources, the Crab Pulsar and Cyg X-1. a) BATSS slew data b) BATSS orbital data c) BAT orbital data d) BAT daily data

The BAT slew survey (BATSS), which uses the same telescope, derives its data from scanning coded aperture imaging as described in Grindlay and Hong (2004). This method of observation results in nearly Poisson-limited sensitivity of the hard X-ray sky by reducing systematic error significantly. Errors resulting from sources being off-axis or only filling a partial coding fraction are also reduced since such sources are frequently fully coded for at least part of the scan. These effects are also independent of field of view and energy band. Thus, although on average BAT spends ~ 17.75 hr in pointing mode vs. ~ 2.90 hr slewing each day, the BATSS total error is only a bit larger on average.

Two of the main motivations behind the BATSS are that 1) the BATSS adds to the completeness of the BAT hard X-ray survey by utilizing the time between BAT pointed exposures and 2) by using the data from individual BAT slews, the time domains that can be explored become as short as ~ 10 s for individual slews and ~ 100 s for data taken over entire orbits, allowing for some features to be seen in the BATSS data that is absent from the BAT data. The timescale differences between BATSS orbital and slew data are shown in Fig. 1, along with comparison to BAT data. These differences allow the exploration of flares on timescales related to how short the BATSS exposure time is in relation to the BAT: ~ 10 s scales for slew vs. orbital data, ~ 100 s for orbital vs orbital data, and ~ 1000 s for orbital vs daily data. Additionally, BATSS covers a larger portion of the sky than BAT's pointing mode each day, observing nearly the entire sky in the same 15-50keV band daily with detection sensitivity of ~ 3 mCrab. (Copete 2012).

The BATSS data has been made accessible due in large part to the complex data pipeline constructed by Antonio Copete, detailed in Copete (2012). The pipeline is written in the Interactive Data Language (IDL) and has been designed to be a modular system. At each of its independent stages, it handles analysis tasks including the downlinking of data from the Swift-BAT telescope to the Malindi ground station, preprocessing uncalibrated event-by-event data in real time, and creating a series of high-level data products. Among the high-level products is a database of candidate γ -ray bursts and transient sources, the latter of which is used throughout this study. The products are built from the analysis of detections in single-slew and multi-slew observations (orbital, daily, etc.) and stored on the BATSS hardware system at the Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics (CfA).

2.2. The Automated Flare Detection Algorithm

In order to find flares, BATSS data is compared to temporally adjacent BAT data of longer timescales and an automated flare detection is run to pick out flares. In particular, three sets of data are compared: BATSS orbital data is compared to BAT daily averages, BATSS orbital data is compared to BAT orbital data, and BATSS slew data is compared to BAT orbital data. By comparing BATSS data with BAT data in this way, points of exceptionally high flux with respect to the average flux reported near that time can be found. An additional reason for comparing to BAT data is the smaller error bars that result from the much longer integration times.

BAT data was downloaded from the monitor web page on the NASA website¹ and BATSS data was collected from the BATSS machine at the CfA through an ssh connection. While the BAT data is stored in the form of a single FITS file containing all nine years of data, BATSS data is split into individual FITS files corresponding to single-slew or multi-slew exposures, which are compressed with gzip. Since there are currently upwards of 10000 slew detection files, and about half as many orbital detection files per source, the data files was kept compressed, with only a few being

¹ <http://swift.gsfc.nasa.gov/docs/swift/results/transients/>

FIG. 2.— Lightcurves of Cygnus X-1 over about 2 weeks of data in the year 2008, with BATSS orbital data (red) plotted on top of BAT daily data (blue). a) All BAT and BATSS data for the week b) All BAT data with only BATSS data that were counted as flares. The 3σ difference can be confirmed by eye.

uncompressed at a time, when data was being read.

For a given source, BATSS files were opened one at a time and had their observation time, exposure length, flux, and statistical error read. Systematic error was calculated using the formula in Copete (2012):

$$\sigma_{sys}^2 = 2.96 \times 10^{-4} \text{cts/cm}^2/\text{s} \cdot S_{src} \left(\frac{T}{100\text{s}} \right)^{-1} + (4.19\% S_{src})^2 \quad (1)$$

where S_{src} is the flux in counts per second per cm^2 and T is exposure time in seconds. The total error for the difference between BAT and BATSS data can then be determined by adding the systematic and statistical errors in quadrature, i.e. $\sigma_{total} = \sqrt{\sigma_{stat}^2 + \sigma_{sys}^2}$.

To find these values from the BAT data at the adjacent time, observation time, exposure length, flux, and total error were read from the BAT fits file for the same source. Observation times for both BAT and BATSS were converted to Modified Julian Date (MJD) if they were in *Swift* Mission Elapsed Time (MET) using the conversion on the *Swift* website. For comparison to BAT daily data, the day on which the BATSS orbital detection occurred was found and the values associated with that day were used when comparing to the orbital data, whereas for comparison to BAT orbital data, the average of the BAT data (weighted by size of error) which corresponded to times before and after the BATSS detection was used.

After locating the BAT and BATSS data points that were the closest to each other in time, their fluxes and total errors were converted to an instrument-independent unit (mCrab), since counts per second per cm^2 differed slightly between pointing mode and slewing due to different methodologies. We could then calculate the flux difference ($F_{BATSS} - F_{BAT}$), along with the error in this combined value, which can be estimated by adding the BAT and BATSS errors in quadrature. Points where the flux difference is more than $3\sigma_{combined}$ are considered to be flares. Figure 2 shows two lightcurves demonstrating what our flares look like.

I implemented the entire algorithm in Python. The package **astropy.io.fits** greatly assisted in handling the FITS files, while **mpi4py** allowed me to parallelize my code which was especially helpful for certain tasks which originally took nearly a day to run.

3. ANALYSIS

3.1. Power Law fits to Flare Size Distribution

As previously mentioned, a power law can be expected for a given source's flare size distribution (number of flares N vs. the flux of the flare S above the local average). Equivalently, a linear fit should emerge for a $\log_{10}N$ vs. $\log_{10}S$ ($\log N - \log S$) distribution, where the power in the first instance becomes the slope. We bin the data into 9 bins, a number chosen by eye, as this seems to on the whole create the smoothest distributions.

We only fit the upper half of bins, as the distributions are only linear in this regime due to a low cutoff. Our method of detecting flares ensures that flares are only recognized when their flux is 3σ greater than the noise in a given measurement. It is possible that this results in a selection bias against smaller flares, which may lead to lower flare numbers in the lower bins than occur in reality. Furthermore, a physical low cutoff may exist for flaring(?), but this is not implied by our data and should be investigated further by future observations with increased sensitivities.

We also do not use the last bin in the fit. This is done to avoid the low statistics at the high end that occur with equally sized bins, since low flare counts could potentially invalidate our power law fits. Specifically, since our fitting

FIG. 3.— Differential distributions of fluence for orbital data with linear fits. The vertical axes are \log_{10} of the number of flares, while the horizontal axes are \log_{10} of the flux in mCrab. The black histograms are the number of flares in each bin. The red curves are the best power law fit with cutoffs. α is the slope of the red curve and n is the total number of flares used in the histogram.

function factors in Poisson error, bins with only a few counts would have error bars that are underestimated (e.g. for $n = 1$, the error is $\sqrt{1} \neq$ the Gaussian 1σ value).

Figs. 3-5 show the $\log N$ - $\log S$ distributions for the black hole candidates, pulsars, and low B-field neutron stars, respectively. Table 1 gives α for each object, where $N \propto S^{-\alpha}$, along with the reduced χ^2 value and the number of flares detected and used to make the histograms. As can be seen in Table 1, not every fit is meaningful, as the reduced χ^2 is either quite high or too low. This is likely a result of using the same method of binning for all datasets and across all timescales, which while maintaining consistency, may not be optimal in all cases.

Object Name	orbital vs. daily			orbital vs. orbital			slew vs. orbital		
	α	χ_{red}^2	# of flares	α	χ_{red}^2	# of flares	α	χ_{red}^2	# of flares
CygX-1	4.154 ± 0.435	0.808	432	3.035 ± 0.356	3.265	267	2.701 ± 0.656	0.091	106
GRS1915+105	2.076 ± 0.437	1.949	172	1.963 ± 0.433	0.494	130	1.992 ± 0.560	5.306	134
GX339-4	1.986 ± 0.538	0.535	175	1.843 ± 0.620	0.678	133	2.429 ± 0.691	1.337	132
MAXIJ1659-152	3.077 ± 0.673	0.801	87	2.534 ± 0.858	1.200	75	1.461 ± 0.645	0.498	111
CenX-3	2.245 ± 0.368	1.596	360	3.665 ± 0.530	1.019	179	3.118 ± 0.714	0.406	129
HerX-1	2.804 ± 0.310	2.419	405	0.307 ± 0.333	0.047	210	2.860 ± 0.617	1.502	177
MAXIJ1409-619	3.324 ± 0.834	0.804	83	2.534 ± 0.983	2.231	71	1.286 ± 0.761	2.597	83
VelaX-1	1.964 ± 0.144	4.215	1099	2.160 ± 0.175	1.764	829	2.529 ± 0.153	3.628	1330
4U1700-377	1.627 ± 0.106	3.304	1579	1.662 ± 0.124	4.074	1301	1.801 ± 0.148	4.141	1100
GX17+2	3.498 ± 0.467	2.358	271	3.224 ± 0.692	1.384	180	3.725 ± 0.732	0.529	141
GX349+2	3.233 ± 0.443	1.289	342	2.188 ± 0.525	2.247	230	3.545 ± 0.480	0.545	372
ScoX-1	0.923 ± 0.123	5.230	1361	1.299 ± 0.149	2.003	1023	0.954 ± 0.152	0.196	816

TABLE 1
POWER LAWS FOR THE DIFFERENTIAL FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTIONS OF EACH OBJECT'S FLARES ON THREE TIMESCALES.

3.2. Two-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

The Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test is another useful way of determining how similar two datasets are. Unlike our power law fits, which relied on numerous parameters, such as number of bins, bin sizes, and cutoffs at either end, the K-S test is non-parametric. It allows the calculation of the probability that a chosen univariate dataset comes from the same parent dataset as a continuous model (in the one-sample case) or a second dataset (the two-sample K-S test).

FIG. 4.— Same as Fig. 3 but for the pulsars.

FIG. 5.— Same as Fig. 3 but for the low B-field neutron stars.

The K-S test calculates a parameter called the K-S statistic D_n , which is defined by:

$$D_n \equiv [|F_1(x) - F_2(x)|] \quad (2)$$

or equivalently the supremum of the difference between the empirical cumulative distribution functions (ECDF) of the datasets being compared. The ECDFs are created by taking an ordered list (our flare sizes) and using it as the set of x-values for a step function that jumps up by $\frac{1}{n}$ each step, where n = number of flares.

Since the average flare size of individual distribution could be quite different from each other, the ECDFs were often very far from one another, resulting in most p-values being ~ 0 . However, since the KS-test tests both shape and location, the low p-values may have resulted from only one of these being low. If the ECDFs are normalized by having each divided by the median, it is possible to use the two-sample KS-test to compare the shape of the distribution only. The null hypothesis is then that the datasets come from parent distributions of the same shape. The normalized empirical cumulative distribution functions for each source are calculated and plotted in Figs. 6-8. The p-value resulting from the K-S test for each pair of sources is given in Table 2.

K-S Test for Orbital Data												
	CygX-1	GRS1915	GX339	MAXIJ1659	CenX-3	HerX-1	MAXIJ1409	VelaX-1	4U1700	GX17	GX349	ScoX-1
CygX-1	1.000	0.031	0.004	0.028	0.022	0.247	0.324	0	0	0.002	0	0
GRS1915	0.031	1.000	0.370	0.670	0.260	0.159	0.287	0	0.002	0.370	0.476	0
GX339	0.004	0.370	1.000	0.987	0.150	0.111	0.603	0	0	0.351	0.209	0
MAXIJ1659	0.028	0.670	0.987	1.000	0.355	0.287	0.546	0.001	0.001	0.777	0.755	0
CenX-3	0.022	0.260	0.150	0.355	1.000	0.786	0.532	0	0	0.318	0.386	0
HerX-1	0.247	0.159	0.111	0.287	0.786	1.000	0.648	0	0	0.178	0.134	0
MAXIJ1409	0.324	0.287	0.603	0.546	0.532	0.648	1.000	0.075	0.057	0.620	0.480	0.030
VelaX-1	0	0	0	0.001	0	0	0.075	1.000	0.703	0	0	0.186
4U1700	0	0.002	0	0.001	0	0	0.057	0.703	1.000	0	0	0.134
GX17	0.002	0.370	0.351	0.777	0.318	0.178	0.620	0	0	1.000	0.958	0
GX349	0	0.476	0.209	0.755	0.386	0.134	0.480	0	0	0.958	1.000	0
ScoX-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.030	0.186	0.134	0	0	1.000

TABLE 2

K-S STATISTIC FOR EACH TWO SAMPLE K-S TEST ON ORBITAL-DAILY DATA. 0 MEANS 0.000, BUT THE SIGNIFICANT FIGURES WERE DROPPED TO MAKE THE TABLE A BIT EASIER TO INTERPRET. SOURCE NAMES WERE ABBREVIATED TO MAKE THE TABLE FIT. THE K-S TEST RESULTS OF FLARES ON THE OTHER TWO TIMESCALES GENERATE SIMILAR TABLES.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Signature of X-ray Source Type?

Looking at the power laws and K-S test results, it is uncertain whether a relation between objects of the same kind exists or not. The K-S test results occasionally show high probability of similar sources' flare distributions coming from the same underlying distribution, such as in the case of black holes GX 339-4 and MAXIJ1659-152, where the p-value is .987, or for low B-field neutron stars GX349+2 and GX17+2, where the p-value is .958. However, in multiple instances the p-value is low enough to reject the null hypothesis that flares from objects of the same kind have the same underlying size distributions. Furthermore, p-values too high to reject the null hypothesis arise between different kinds of objects, as in the case of MAXI J1659-152, a black hole candidate, and GX 17+2, a low B-field neutron star, whose K-S test p-value is 0.777. Furthermore, the methodology of the K-S test might be called into question as well. Since the K-S test is most sensitive when the largest difference is close to the center, dividing by the median may weaken the test (Stephens 1974). We might consider the Cramer-von Mises test or Anderson-Darling test, since these are similar to the K-S test but allow for altering the mean to the same value explicitly, and are also found to generally be more sensitive (Hou 2009). Lastly, it seems that low numbers of flares for a source led to it having higher p-values with respect to all other sources, which may follow from how we conduct the K-S test.

The power laws also show inconclusive results. There again exist some cases of very similar α values between sources of the same kind, but there are nearly as many matches between different kinds of sources. Additionally, looking at the reduced χ^2 values, one can see that there are not very many strong fits. These values indicate that the data is overfit in some cases, and far from linear in others, indicating that the fitting function may need non-constant parameters. That is, assuming that a power law indeed exists for differential flare fluence distributions, suboptimal parameters may have been selected for the fits.

4.2. Comparison with Previous Statistics

Many previous analyses of X-ray flare size distributions exist. While the majority of these pertain to solar X-ray flares, several studies have been published concerning the compact objects examined here. Negoro et al. (1995) looked at Cygnus X-1's peak intensities, finding α for peak intensities to be very steep, $\alpha_P \approx 7.1$. As the power law for peak intensities is predicted to be related to the power law for fluence (Aschwanden 2013), we would expect a steep fluence

FIG. 6.— ECDFs of the black holes used for the two-sample KS-test. a) The original ECDF. b) The ECDF after dividing by the median. Notice that each plot consequently passes through the point (1,0.5).

FIG. 7.— Same as Fig. 6 but for pulsars.

FIG. 8.— Same as Fig. 6 but for low B-field neutron stars.

power law α_E in our data. Indeed, α_E for our BATSS orbital vs. BAT daily data is the steepest value we found ($\alpha_E \approx 4.154$, and this value remains relatively high on the other two timescales. A recent paper by Neilsen (2013) also looks at the power law of a black hole (Sgr A*). Looking on timescales ~ 26000 s, he finds that $\alpha_E \approx 1.5 \pm 0.2$, which matches my values for GRS1915+105 and GX339-4 somewhat, but is quite different than my other two values (including CygX-1's). It might be worth noting that the fractal-diffusive self-organized criticality (FD-SOC) model for accretion predicts $\alpha_E \approx 1.5$ (Aschwanden 2013), although it also predicts $\alpha_P \approx 1.67$, which is quite different from Negoro's result. Regarding pulsars, Melatos (2008) predicts α_E as high as 2.4, which is consistent with most of my pulsar values.

It is also interesting to note that the power laws for all my sources are roughly consistent across all three timescales. As the results of this study line up for the most part with flare analyses on longer timescales, they could be interpreted as evidence for the FD-SOC model, which very generally predicts similar power laws over all time and length scales.

5. CONCLUSION

We have found that the BATSS observations can be used to explore the faint, high-variability phase space of hard X-ray transients, as predicted by Copete, 2012. We investigated flares on several different timescales for three kinds of sources: black holes, pulsars, and low B-field neutron stars. Based on theoretical predictions, we expected a power law in the flare distributions and found the values for the best fit power laws. Our results unfortunately do not indicate that fluence distributions of X-ray flares on short timescales are strong signatures of an X-ray source's type. However, such a relation might exist, and was not found due to errors in our statistical methods. Also, on the whole, our power law fits did seem to be in line with the values from other studies, but this was a likely result given the large errors in our power law estimates relative to the differences in the sources' power laws.

Future work related to this study would be the inclusion of more sources, which would increase the significance of any relations between objects of the same kind. It might also be beneficial to reparameterize the linear fitting (changing number of bins, bin sizes, cutoffs, etc.) and investigate why the normal K-S test was so weak (or use one of the other tests previously mentioned).

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